

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Available online at :

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2issue-6-july-2014>

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CONSUMER'S BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF BRANDED GROCERY PRODUCTS IN ORGANIZED AND UNORGANIZED SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

This study aims at to examine the “consumer’s buying behaviour of branded grocery products in organized and unorganized sector” in Madurai, a tier II city and also aims to study the changing retail market scenario. The speed in which the transition takes place from unorganized sector to organized stores, due to increasing self-service and changing consumers behaviour in buying branded grocery items. The growing organised stores such as malls and self serviced stores act as stimulator of buying, by the customers. In this study the data collected through a questionnaire to know the consumer perception and preference about branded grocery items and also to find out the factors which are forced customers to shift from buying unbranded to branded grocery items and from organised stores.

Keywords: Grocery Products, Buying behaviour, Branded Grocery, Organised stores

INTRODUCTION

In earlier days people used to buy grocery items in loose, unbranded mostly from the local shops. The perception of the people was that those traders were easily approached and believed to be selling quality products at lesser prices. But due to the change in consumer’s life style and due to the increasing advertisement by branded players and impact of media in customer’s perception changed the buying behaviour. Some Regional and National retailers started supplying the products after due processing like cleaning and supplying with attractive packing with a brand name. Initially branded essential food items

such as wheat flour, Atta flour, cooking oils, salt etc., are supplied with. Later on branded sales extended to many grocery items and right now the customers are blessed with almost every item including all types of branded dals, rice, all powders like chilli powder etc. for daily use.

"The Indian retail industry is presently one of the world's top five retail markets in terms of economic value and the industry is experiencing exponential growth, with retail development taking place not just in major cities and metros, but also in smaller towns," KPMG² in India, said. In this scenario, creating consumer loyalty is now a whole new challenge. These demographic shifts have also created the need for leaders who can keep pace with change and identify with and predict future demand.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Brand according to Kotler⁴ is name, term, sign, or design, or a combination of them, intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of competitors. A brand is a complex symbol. It can convey up to six levels of meaning, Attributes, Benefits, Values, Culture, Personality, and User. Brand management brings about clear differentiation between products, ensures consumer loyalty and preferences which lead to a greater market share. A brand is a name, symbol, design, or mark that enhances the value of a product beyond its functional value. Generic / unbranded products are known to the consumers on the basis of their ingredients as they are plain packed.

Now-a-days the buying behavior of consumers in India has largely changed. Education, age, income, economic scenario, media and technology play dominant role in deciding the way people shop, according to a report by the Retailers Association of India (RAI)¹ and consultancy firm KPMG. The report, based on a study done to understand the buying behavior of Indian consumers, states that the Indian consumer today is more educated. Park et al (2004)⁴ concluded that television advertisements can highly influence women buying behaviors along with information received from their friends (Sheers 2007). According to Zelezny et al,(2000)⁹ studies on the women buying behaviour dimensions suggest that females are more pro-environmental while shopping than their male counterparts.

"The Indian retail industry is presently one of the world's top five retail markets in terms of economic value and the industry is experiencing exponential growth, with retail development taking place not just in major cities and metros, but also in smaller towns," KPMG (2005)² in India, said. According to the report, rapid urbanization and lifestyle changes have increased Buying behaviour of BoP (bottom of the pyramid) consumers who have an average household income below Rs 1,00,000 a year has also changed thanks to impact of government schemes. Retailers are focusing on satisfaction on key service parameters and loyalty, which can be driven by strengthening front end operations. Amid growing brand consciousness, companies may also cater to strong 'local' tastes of urban consumers, which may involve tweak product, marketing and supply chain as well, according to the report.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Now with the globalisation and gates opened up for international retail giants, a large chunk of these customers especially youth is changing the way people are shopping and this has a direct implication on various aspects of shopping such as the choice of brands. The local players who sell unbranded items losing their market share and the branded market gaining the momentum. In this scenario it is felt that the consumer preference towards branded/ unbranded grocery items in organised and unorganised shops to be studied, which may useful for the local players raise their standards.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The main focus of the problem is to measure the consumer preference towards branded grocery Items. The study tries to finds out what are the factors that make the branded grocery items attractive.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To identify the factors that to the consumer preference on the branded grocery items.
2. To analyze the factors influencing buying behaviour of grocery items in organised sector.

3. To study the consumer preference towards organised /unorganised retail outlets.

HYPOTHESIS

Null hypothesis were framed and tested for significance to prove the objectives in a systematic manner. The null hypothesis was as follows:

H₀₁ (Null): There is no significant relation between Income level and buying branded grocery items.

H₀₂ (Null): There is no significant relation between education level and buying branded grocery items in organised stores.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This research has been categorized to be Descriptive because the major purpose of this research is the description of the factors as it exists. It is used to find the relation between two variables. Buying behaviour of branded grocery items from organised stores and factors influencing that behaviour.

SAMPLE DESIGN

Universe Type	: Infinite
Sampling Method	: Convenience
Sampling Unit	: North Madurai.

The primary data was collected by a five-point scale questionnaire containing 19 statements was used. The scale used was Likert's five-point scale where the respondents had to fill one choice ranging from "Highly agree" to "Highly Disagree". The questionnaires were filled by 145 respondents. After collecting the data, it was tabulated in Excel sheet and analyzed by using Chi square analysis and Correlation Analysis.

Secondary data was collected from Internet, books, newspapers, journals, business magazines etc.

SAMPLE

The questionnaire was distributed to 150 people, 50 each in three places of North Madurai, between the period April 2014 to June 2014 out of which 2, were incomplete, 3, not returned and hence 145 were taken for analysis.

FORMULA APPLIED

This study uses the Chi Square Analysis to test the hypothesis 1 (H₀₁), Correlation Coefficient for hypothesis 2 (H₀₂) and Weighted Average for ranking the factors. The formula used to calculate the Chi Square Analysis is given by:

$$\text{Chi-Square } (\chi^2) = \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where, O = Observed frequency; and E = Expected Frequency

$E = \frac{\text{Row Total} * \text{Column Total}}{\text{Grand Total}}$

Exhibit - 1

Income Level Buying branded grocery	Fully agree	Agree	Indifferent	Disagree	Fully Disagree	Total
Less than Rs 10000	9	10	8	6	4	37
Rs 10000 - 20000	8	6	7	5	7	33
Rs 20001 - 30000	6	8	4	6	1	25
Rs 30001 - 40000	6	9	7	4	4	30
Above 40000	4	5	3	5	3	20
Total	33	38	29	26	19	145

Source: Primary data

To find out relationship between Income level and Consumer buying behaviour of branded grocery items using Chi square analysis

O	E	O-E	(O-E)²	(O-E)²/E
9	8.42	0.58	0.34	0.04
10	9.70	0.30	0.09	0.01
8	7.40	0.60	0.36	0.05
6	6.63	-0.63	0.40	0.06
4	4.85	-0.85	0.72	0.15
8	7.51	0.49	0.24	0.03
6	8.65	-2.65	7.02	0.81
7	6.60	0.40	0.16	0.02
5	5.91	-0.91	0.83	0.14
7	4.32	2.68	7.18	1.66
6	5.69	0.31	0.10	0.02
8	6.55	1.45	2.10	0.32
4	5.00	-1.00	1.00	0.20
6	4.48	1.52	2.31	0.52
1	3.28	-2.28	5.20	1.58
6	6.83	-0.83	0.69	0.10
9	7.86	1.14	1.30	0.17
7	6.00	1.00	1.00	0.17
4	5.38	-1.38	1.90	0.35
4	3.93	0.07	0.00	0.00
4	4.55	-0.55	0.30	0.07
5	5.24	-0.24	0.06	0.01
3	4.00	-1.00	1.00	0.25
5	3.59	1.41	1.99	0.55
3	2.62	0.38	0.14	0.06
				7.34

Calculated Value = 7.34

Degrees of Freedom = (5-1) * (5-1) = 4 * 4 = 16

Level of significance = 5% or 0.05

Table Value = 26. 296, which is greater than Calculated Value of 7.34

Hence the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected.

Therefore it is concluded that there is significant relationship between the income level and buying branded grocery items by the people.

The second hypothesis of the research was as follows:

H₀₂ (Null): There is no relationship between Education level of the respondents and buying behaviour of branded grocery products in organised stores.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is relationship between Education level of the respondents and buying behaviour of branded grocery products in organised stores.

This hypothesis was also tested on the basis of the responses of 145 respondents using Correlation Coefficient Method.

The formula used to calculate the Correlation Coefficient is given by

$$r = \frac{\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{N \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{N \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}} \quad \text{Where } x = X - \bar{X}, \quad y = Y - \bar{Y}$$

Where, r = Correlation Coefficient [X represents: Education Level (For H₀₂) and Y represents: Buying branded grocery products in organised stores]

Exhibit 2

X	Y	x = X - \bar{x}	x ²	y = Y - \bar{y}	y ²	xy
33	36	4	16	7	49	28
21	42	-8	64	13	169	-104
32	28	3	9	-1	1	-3
40	23	11	121	-6	36	-66
19	16	-10	100	13	169	130
145	145	0	310	0	424	-15

Source: Primary data

$$\sum X = 145; \sum Y = 145$$

$$\bar{x} = \sum X / N = 145/5 = 29 \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{y} = \sum Y / N = 145/5 = 29$$

$$r = \frac{N \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{N \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{N \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}}$$

$$r = \frac{5(-24) - (0)(0)}{\sqrt{5(310) - (0)^2} \sqrt{5(424) - (0)^2}}$$

$$r = \frac{-75}{(39.37)(46.04)} = -0.0414$$

From the value it is observed that there is a negative correlation between the two variables, hence null hypothesis (H₀₂) is rejected. Hence there is relation between education level and buying behaviour of

branded grocery items in organised stores, i.e when the education level increases people used to buy branded grocery items in organised stores.

CALCULATION OF WEIGHTED AVERAGE METHOD

To give rank for each variable used in this study which helps to prioritize the factors affecting buying behaviour of branded grocery items in organized stores based on the weightage assigned to those variables, from the responses.

- Fully agree - 5
- Agree - 4
- Indifferent - 3
- Disagree - 2
- Fully Disagree - 1

Ranking based on Weighted Average Method

Variables	Weight	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Average= Total/N N = 145	Rank
High Quality.		215	180	27	56	20	498	3.43	2
More Quantity.		190	144	15	90	21	460	3.17	4
Brand image.		230	168	18	64	19	499	3.44	1
Reliability of the product.		205	172	24	76	15	492	3.39	3
Less time taken		160	132	6	94	31	423	2.92	5

Source: Primary Data

FINDINGS

Exhibit 3

Variables	Buying Behaviour	Interpretation
Income Level	$\chi^2 = 7.34$	Calculated value is less than table value, hence there is significant relationship between the income level and buying branded grocery items.
Education Level	$r = -0.04$	Negative correlation; When education level increases buying branded grocery items in organised sector also increases.

When the income level increases the customers tends to buy branded grocery items. Also the education level also influencing buying behaviours, customers buying branded grocery items in organized stores.

Based on the weighted average it is observed that the first preference on buying grocery items in organised stores is the brand image, many a time the some popular companies who provide all grocery items in the clearly packed with brand name is perceived as best for their use.

The second factor because of which they buy branded items is that of the high quality of branded companies. Majority of the customers felt that the branded grocery items are of good quality compared to unbranded items which attracts the respondents to buy the products. Next reason for which the respondents purchase branded grocery items is the reliability of the items in respect of weight, no damage

or no wastage from the branded items as normally it is packed with air tight packing which makes the respondents to buy.

Regarding quantity of the branded grocery items, from the weighted average rating given by the customers, it finds at fourth place indicating the quantity is less when they buy branded grocery items. Also this implies that the respondents are given less consideration to the quantity when they buy branded grocery items. Lastly the time taken for buying branded grocery items in organised store the majority of the respondents disagreeing with the factor and with the weighted average value being very low and with highest difference among the factors, indicating that the time taken is more in the case of organised store. The Service factors related to organised stores which increases buying behaviour of branded grocery items include, Self Service, Transaction costs, and Promotional discounts.

CONCLUSION

From the above study, it can be concluded that there is a shift from buying unbranded grocery items to branded grocery items by the people even in tier II city like Madurai. The factors influencing this shift are mainly due to the increasing educational level and increasing income level.

The few factors which are influential for the shift are brand image, high reliability and quality. The respondents indicated their preference is more on cleanliness and packed products with brand value. Gone are those days where people used to buy the grocery items from the nearby store or the local players, now they want more hygienic products even in grocery items, Hence the unbranded players have to concentrate on those aspects to grow their business.

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ANNEXURE: 1

CONSUMER'S BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF BRANDED GROCERY ITEMS IN ORGANIZED AND UNORGANISED STORES

Personal Data:

1. Name of the Respondent:
2. Age (in completed years):
3. Marital Status : Married Unmarried
4. Academic Qualifications : Less than 10th Upto 12th
 UG PG
 Professional
5. Monthly Income Level (in Rs) : Less than 10000 10000 - 20000
 20001 – 30000 30001 - 40000
 above 40000

Indicate your answers with reference to each of the following statements about your buying behaviour by marking a tick mark [✓] against that column.

6. Your awareness about the branded grocery items
 Yes No
7. Normally you purchase branded grocery items
 Fully Agree Agree Indifferent
 Disagree Fully Disagree
8. Nature of Purchase decision: Impulsive Planned purchase
9. Factors influencing purchase of branded grocery items:
 Media Advertisement Friends & relatives
 Offers Others
10. Normally where you purchase your branded grocery items
 Organised Store Unorganised Store
11. Reason for purchase in organised store:
 Less Price Return Policy. Transaction costs
 Self Service Promotional discounts
12. Factors influencing purchase of branded grocery items in organised retail shops:
 Media Advertisement Friends & relatives
 Offers Others
13. Your educational level influencing purchase of branded grocery items in organised retail shops:
 Fully Agree Agree Indifferent
 Disagree Fully Disagree

Indicate the extent to which each of the following statements you agree with buying Branded Grocery items in organised store using the five point scale by making a tick mark [√] against that column.

	Factors	Fully Agree	Agree	No idea	Disagree	Fully Disagree
14	High Quality.					
15	More Quantity					
16	Brand image.					
17	Reliability of the product.					
18	Less time taken					

19. Any Other suggestion: